

Report 2022 of the DDC at DKRZ

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1. Summary

The total DDC data volume provided by IPCC DDC hosted at DKRZ has increased from 1.7 PBytes to 1.9 PBytes due to the ongoing long-term archival of the AR6 datasets. The volume for the AR6 Reference data archive at the end of 2022 was 118 TBytes, where 35 TBytes belong to SR1.5 datasets from the HAPPI project and 83 TBytes to AR6 CMIP6 input datasets. Other shares are 1.6 PBytes in the AR5 Reference Archive, ca. 1 TByte in the AR4 Reference Archive, and ≤ 10 GBytes each in the Reference Archives for FAR, SAR, and TAR.

IPCC DDC users downloaded ca. 249 TBytes and 467 000 datasets in 2022 with mean monthly downloads of 39 000 datasets/month and 21 TBytes/month. The trend of decreasing data downloads have continued, which are caused by the decreasing AR5 data downloads, which dominate the DDC statistics. The ESGF share of the data downloads remain > 90 %. Download volumes for data of all previous ARs show decreases from 2021 to 2022 of: ca. -90 % for SAR, ca. -71 % for TAR, ca. -29 % for AR4, and ca. -41 % for AR5. AR6 data downloads increase against the trend by a factor of 54. No data for selected areas on storage media was requested by DDC in 2022. DDC users requested no data for selected areas on storage media in 2022.

71 % of the downloads were from users located in Asia followed by European users with 17 % and North American users with 11 %, leaving less than 1 % for users located in Africa, South America and Australia.

2. Evolution of data access

From mid 2020 to January 2021, massive downloads of a single dataset from a single European ESGF user occurred. These technical downloads were carefully eliminated from the statistics.

The total downloads in 2022, 249 TBytes, are 55 % of the downloads in 2021 (**Figure 1**), after the total downloads had decreased by 50 % from 2020 to 2021. The interest in the CMIP5 datasets underpinning AR5 declines with the increased stability of the available CMIP6 datasets. Especially, in the second half of 2022 the monthly downloads decreased. The volume was downloaded in ca. 467 000 individual datasets. The mean monthly data downloads are ca. 21 TBytes/month and ca. 39 000 datasets/month.

Figure 1: Total data download counts and volumes per months over the last three years in GBytes from the IPCC DDC reference archive.

Compared to the total downloads from DKRZ's long-term archive, the download volume from the DDC Reference Data Archives contributes 60 % to the total download volume from DKRZ's long-term archive, while it accounts for only 30 % of the content. Based on the number of dataset downloads, DDC's share of the downloads from DKRZ's long-term archive is > 90 % with a content share of 80 %. The data contained in the DDC are the most popular datasets in DKRZ's long-term archive.

3. Geographical distribution of data access

For the IPCC DDC AR5 data, direct data access at the DKRZ and access via ESGF are supported. Downloads from ESGF dominate the statistics with > 90 % of the downloads. The ESGF file downloads in 2022 were merged with the DDC continental download information (**Figure 2**). As an information on the number of active users is not available for the dominating ESGF downloads, no reliable information on active users can be provided for 2022.

Figure 2: Number of dataset downloads (download counts) per continent for 2022.

The download counts per continent show that 71 % of the total downloads were from Asian users followed by 17 % European and 11 % North American users (**Figure 2**). The remaining 1 % is distributed between African, South American and Australian users. Total download from Africa, Asia and South America, which can be roughly regarded as developing and economy-in-transition countries, are equal to the Asian share of 71 % of the total download counts. The percentage of downloads from Europe among the ESGF portal users is half the value among the DDC portal users. The observation for North American users is the opposite with a percentage of only 3% among the DDC portal users.

3.1 Data on storage media

No data for selected areas on storage media was requested by DDC in 2022.

4. Data access by category AR

The monthly download rates in 2022 from the IPCC DDC Reference Data Archive were dominated

by AR5 downloads as in the previous years (**Figure 3**; online monthly download statistics¹). The majority of AR5 data (> 90 %) were downloaded via DKRZ's DDC ESGF data node. The numbers show a total download volume of ca. 248 TByte for AR5 in 2022, which is ca. 59 % of the download volume of the previous year. Users CMIP data interests are shifting from CMIP5 towards CMIP6 datasets. The individual 465 000 AR5 file downloads in 2022 are 57 % of the downloads in 2021.

Figure 3: Total annual data download counts (left) and volumes in GBytes (right) over the last five years for the different DDC reference archives (without FAR; AR6 includes SR1.5).

The download numbers in 2022 for the oldest ARs show significant decreases compared to 2021: The downloads for SAR and TAR dropped to ca. 20 % of their 2021 values and the download number for AR4 datasets is ca. 30% of that for the previous year. The most recent datasets related to AR6 consist of SR1.5 model data from the HAPPI project until 2021 and an increasing number of dataset downloads from the CMIP6 input datasets, which are still in the process of long-term archiving. The download numbers in 2022 increased significantly and are 8 times the download numbers in 2021. The 2021-2022 trends in download volumes show decreases related to the 2021 values: to 9 % for SAR, to 29 % for TAR, to 70 % for AR4, and to 59 % for AR5. The downloaded volume of AR6-related datasets in 2022 is 54 times the value in 2021. Because of the relative low total download volume for AR6, this increase can only slightly compensate for the decrease in AR5 data downloads. The total DDC data downloads have decreased from 2021 to 2022.

¹ Online monthly download statistics are available at:

https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR6
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR5
https://cera-www.dkrz.de/WDCC/ui/cerasearch/statistics?type=downloads_by_domain&domain=IPCC-DDC_AR4

5. Review of user queries

User requests are directed to the DDC Partner DKRZ and for AR5 data partly to the ESGF support. A separation of user requests on IPCC DDC issues is not possible. The joint DDC support infrastructure was set up end of 2021. No requests were forwarded to DKRZ from there.

In parallel to the regular user support channels, additional requests were sent to individuals at the modelling centers or at the data centers.

6. News and activities

83 TBytes of AR6 CMIP6 input datasets were archived in the AR6 Reference Data Archive in 2022, several additional CMIP6 input datasets and AR6 intermediate datasets are in the process of metadata curation and data archival (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4: Data long-term archival in the AR6 Reference Data Archive during 2022 (top: CMIP6 input datasets, bottom: intermediate datasets).